

**THE INFLUENCE OF CONTENT MARKETING STRATEGY AND CUSTOMER
ENGAGEMENT IN SOCIAL MEDIA ON FIRM PERFORMANCE OF
SELECTED SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISE (SMEs) IN
TAGUM CITY, DAVAO DEL NORTE**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 8

Pages: 1087-1096

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2416

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13843386

Manuscript Accepted: 08-26-2024

The Influence of Content Marketing Strategy and Customer Engagement in Social Media on Firm Performance of Selected Small and Medium Enterprise (SMEs) in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte

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Abstract

This study was examined to determine the impact of content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media on the firm performance of selected small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. A total of 229 managers and owners of businesses in Tagum City, Davao del Norte, were chosen to participate in the study. Research questionnaires were adapted as an instrument in a quantitative, non-experimental study employing correlational methodology. Standard deviation, Pearson-r, mean, and regression analysis are the statistical methods engaged in this study. Based on the results, it was found that the respondents had a high level of content marketing strategy, a high level of customer engagement in social media, and a very high level of firm performance. This study discovered a significant relationship between content marketing strategy and firm performance. In addition, a significant relationship between customer engagement in social media and firm performance was determined. In addition, content marketing strategizing context, content production context, content marketing performance measurement context, and content marketing organization domains all had a substantial impact on firm performance. Similarly, the cognitive dimension, emotional dimension, and behavioral dimension domains all influenced firm performance. Finally, the study supported by the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory serves as the main theory, the supported theories are Social Exchange Theory, Marketing Performance Measurement Theory, and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) are the supporting theories.

Keywords: *Master in Business Administration, content marketing strategy, customer engagement in social media, firm performance*

Introduction

The contemporary business landscape places immense emphasis on the performance of companies. Firm performance serves as a vital indicator of an organization's ability to establish efficient systems for consistently delivering products or services that meet and exceed customer expectations. It is a vital metric that reflects a company's overall health and its competitive expertise (Riberolles, 2021, pp. 1-7).

Within this context, content marketing strategies and customer engagement in social media have emerged as critical determinants of firm performance. Content marketing strategies empower brands to create and disseminate relevant, valuable content across digital platforms, basic for achieving strategic objectives, strengthening brand reputation, and nurturing lasting customer relationships (Hollebeek & Macky 2019, p. 27-44). Simultaneously, customer engagement in social media acts as a driver of customer engagement (CE), connecting consumers and companies across various dimensions, including brand love, sentiment analysis, and public participation (Palazon et al. 2019, p. 710-727; Saura et al. 2021, p.108; Lin & Kant 2021, p. 1-14), allowing businesses to build and enhance consumer relationships (Fernandes & Moreira 2019, p. 274-286).

However, it is imperative to recognize that the challenges and dynamics influencing firm performance can vary significantly in different geographical contexts. Since, there was no researcher found any studies in local and international settings that was the reason why the researcher urged to investigate to determine the unique factors influencing firm performance in Tagum City, Davao del Norte.

Substantiated by several studies that content marketing strategy has a significant relationship with firm performance. For instance, research in the pharmaceutical industry emphasizes the profound impact of content marketing, particularly on Facebook, in engaging customers and driving purchasing preferences, leading to increased sales and profitability (Tabiat 2022, p. 349- 355). Similarly, a study highlights content marketing's role in improving sales for SMEs, underlining its potential to enhance firm performance (Sembiring et al. 2022, p. 69-79). Furthermore, research demonstrates that content marketing activities on social media platforms significantly influence brand loyalty and purchase intention, highlighting content marketing strategies' potential to positively impact firm performance (Jafarova & Talon 2022, p. 160-184).

Many studies have documented that customer engagement in social media has a significant relationship with firm performance. A study illuminates the transformative impact of customer engagement in social media advertising as a strategic avenue for businesses, offering unparalleled opportunities for enhancing visibility, driving sales, and elevating brand value (Arora & Sanni 2019, p. 476-499). Furthermore, research findings underscore the transformative impact of a well-crafted social media strategy on organizational performance, associated with benefits including market share growth, robust sales, enhanced profitability, and customer satisfaction, demonstrating the potential benefits of customer engagement in social media in bolstering firm performance (Wu et al. 2020, p. 1185-1193).

Despite the growing recognition of the significance of content marketing strategies and customer engagement in social media in shaping firm performance, a notable research gap exists in the literature. There is a lack of comprehensive insights into these variables' effectiveness, efficiency, and integration in influencing company performance, particularly within localized contexts. Therefore, this study aims to bridge this research gap and provide timely insights to selected small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. By delving into the significance of content marketing strategies and customer engagement in social media within this specific geographical context, this research strives to offer tailored strategies and recommendations. These insights will empower local SMEs to adapt their marketing approaches to align with the unique challenges and opportunities present in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. The urgency of this study is underscored by the pressing need for local SMEs to not only survive but thrive in the face of intense competition within the rapidly evolving business landscape, where digital marketing strategies wield substantial influence.

The primary purpose of this study is to determine which domain in the content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media significantly influences or is a significant determinant of the firm performance of selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte. Specifically, this study aims to assess the level of content marketing strategy among selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte, focusing on the content marketing strategizing context, content production context, content marketing performance measurement context, and content marketing organization. Furthermore, the study seeks to evaluate the level of customer engagement in social media exhibited by selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte, considering the cognitive dimension, emotional dimension, and behavioral dimension. Additionally, it aims to gauge the firm performance of these selected SMEs, focusing on growth and profitability as key performance indicators. The study will also investigate the significant relationships between content marketing strategy, customer engagement in social media, and firm performance among the selected SMEs. Based on the findings, recommendations will be proposed to further enhance their marketing strategies' overall performance.

Methodology

Respondents

The population for this study comprised owners and managers of SMEs located in Tagum City, Davao del Norte, for the year 2023. Tagum City, known for its vibrant entrepreneurial environment, houses 451 SMEs (410 small enterprises and 41 medium enterprises), as reported by the Business Permit and Licensing Bureau of the City Government of Tagum in the Last Quarter of 2023. Slovin's formula was employed to determine the appropriate sample size, considering a 50% margin of error and a 95% confidence level, resulting in a sample size of 208 small and 21 medium enterprises. A 10% allowance was added to mitigate potential non-response, bringing the total sample size to 229 respondents who participated in this study.

The selection of respondents was carried out meticulously through stratified random sampling. The strata were defined based on business size, distinguishing between small and medium enterprises. Inclusion criteria specified that the participating managers or owners must have been managing their businesses for a minimum of twelve (12) months or longer, and their respective enterprises should have been in operation for a similar duration.

Unfortunately, some participants unwillingly participated in the study, as the common exclusion criterion, a participating managers or owners managing their businesses for less than twelve (12) months or longer. And their respective enterprises had not been in operation for a similar duration of twelve (12) months or longer. Moreover, Withdrawal criteria if a qualified respondent wants to withdraw from the study or refuses to answer the questionnaire because of some reasons like the availability of the respondents, the information being too sensitive, it's too much effort and more.

The study was conducted in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. Tagum City, situated in the province of Davao del Norte, offers a compelling setting for this research due to its reputation as an entrepreneurial hotspot. Tagum City has received prestigious accolades, including being named the Most Business-Friendly Local Government Unit (LGU) in the Philippines for the second time during the 47th Philippine Business Conference and Expo (Palicte 2021, p. 1-13). Moreover, in the 5th Davao Region Competitiveness Awarding by the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) on February 22, 2022, Tagum City secured the coveted First Place Overall Most Competitive Component City in the Davao Region. It excelled in various competitiveness indices, including Economic Dynamism, Government Efficiency, Infrastructure, and Resiliency, affirming its commitment to sustainable and inclusive growth (Carpio 2022, p. 1-4).

Instrument

The study used a validated questionnaire, which was adapted to measure the levels of content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media among selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. The questionnaire consists of three parts, each assessing a specific construct.

The first part evaluated the level of content marketing strategy of selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. This section was adapted from the questionnaire used in the study by Koob (2021, p. 1-25). The adapted questionnaire comprises four key variables: content marketing strategizing context (consisting of 4 items), content production context (3 items), content marketing performance measurement context (3 items), and content marketing organization (4 items), resulting in a total of 14 items. To ensure the

questionnaire's appropriateness for the study context, it was modified to align with the local SME setting. Additionally, question items were simplified and, if necessary, translated into the vernacular to enhance respondent comprehension.

Procedure

The study used a quantitative non-experimental research design, explicitly employing a correlational technique, to investigate the influence of content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media on the firm performance of selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte. This research design aligned with the study's quantitative nature and the need to explore relationships between variables without manipulating subject conditions or employing random group assignments (Frey 2018, p. 13-17). By adopting this approach, the study aims to identify and analyze the specific factors within the domains of content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media that substantially influence the firm performance of SMEs in the designated locale, effectively addressing the central research objective.

The data collection process involved several steps to ensure the smooth execution of the study. Initially, official acknowledgment and authorization were obtained from UM Tagum College, including a letter of permission and certification from the Dean of the College and the Program Coordinator of the Graduate School. Following the clearance from UMTC, the researcher sought permission from the Chief Executive Officers and Human Resource Management of various SME head offices to conduct the study within their organizations. Once the necessary permissions were secured, the survey questionnaires were distributed to the selected sample population using the research randomizer. The data collection process included face-to-face interactions and an online or web survey, adhering to a paperless system. This approach allowed respondents to choose the mode of data collection that was most convenient and accessible for them. Throughout the data collection phase, any issues or challenges encountered were documented and addressed promptly to ensure the smooth progression of the study. These experiences were considered to enhance the research process and maintain the quality and validity of the collected data. Owners and Managers who are not After collecting the self-reported data from the respondents, the information was meticulously compiled, tallied, and organized for further analysis. This comprehensive data collection procedure aimed to gather reliable and valid information while adhering to ethical standards and regulatory guidelines.

The statistical tools used for data analysis and interpretation are Mean, Pearson (r), and Multiple Regression Analysis. Mean was used to determine the level of content marketing strategy, customer engagement in social media, and firm performance of selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. Pearson (r) was employed to determine the significance of the relationship between content marketing strategy, customer engagement in social media, and firm performance of selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. Multiple Regression Analysis was used to determine which domain in the content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media significantly influences or is a significant determinant of firm performance.

In adherence to stringent research ethics, this study diligently follows established guidelines and principles to ensure the responsible and ethical conduct of research. Key provisions include obtaining informed consent from all participants, maintaining the privacy and confidentiality of collected data, and upholding integrity and honesty throughout the research process. The research ethics compliance process was rigorously overseen and approved by the University's Institutional Review Board (IRB), evidenced by the issuance of a UMERB certification number. Full compliance with UMERB regulations and acquiring the requisite compliance certificate were prerequisites before the commencement of actual data collection, underscoring the commitment to upholding the highest ethical standards in this research endeavor.

Results and Discussion

Level of Content Marketing Strategy

The results of the mean score for content marketing strategy are presented in Table 1, which resulted in an overall score of 4.15, described as high, with a standard deviation of 0.86. This indicates that SMEs in Tagum City exhibit a high level when it comes to content marketing strategizing context, content production context, content marketing performance measurement context, and content marketing organization. The mean score resulted from the data gathered from highest to lowest indicators: 4.35 or very high for content marketing strategizing context; 4.17 or high for content production context; 4.06 or high for content marketing performance; and 4.01 or high for content marketing organization.

Table 1. *Level of Content Marketing Strategy of selected Small-Medium Enterprises in the Tagum City, Davao del Norte*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Content Marketing Strategizing Context	4.35	0.71	Very High
Content Production Context	4.17	0.89	High
Content Marketing Performance measurement Context	4.06	1.02	High
Content Marketing Organization	4.01	0.99	High
Overall	4.15	0.86	High

Additionally, the highest mean score for content marketing strategizing context indicates that SMEs in Tagum City have encompasses a defined, understandable, long-term content marketing strategy within an organization, along with the extent of managerial and

employee support for this strategic direction, emphasizing clarity and commitment and have a strong meaningful connection with the audience while achieving business objectives efficiently. Hence, not only creates compelling content but also ensures that this content contributes directly to achieving business goals, enhances brand perception, and builds lasting relationships with its audience.

This study conformed to the theory of Marketing Performance Measurement Theory by Clark (2007, p.36-63), this is vital for understanding how marketing activities, such as content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media, influence firm performance. Moreover, the theory enables an evaluation of how SMEs measure the effectiveness of their content marketing efforts and clarifies how content creation, strategizing, and performance measurement contribute to growth and profitability, which are key components of firm performance.

Level of Customer Engagement in Social Media

The results of the mean score for customer engagement in social media are presented in Table 2 with an overall score of 4.01, described as high with a standard deviation of 1.12. This result indicates that the respondents exhibit a high level of customer engagement in social media in terms of cognitive dimension, emotional dimension, and emotional dimension which collectively contribute to a highly dynamic and driven mindset within SMEs. The highest to lowest indicators are as follows: 4.03 or higher for the behavioral dimension; 4.02 or higher for the cognitive dimension; and 3.99 for the emotional dimension.

Table 2. *Level of Customer Engagement in Social Media of selected Small-Medium Enterprises in the Tagum City, Davao del Norte*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Cognitive Dimension	4.02	1.11	High
Emotional Dimension	3.99	1.16	High
Behavioral Dimension	4.03	1.14	High
Overall	4.01	1.12	High

The table shows the behavioral dimension has the highest score this indicates that customers are encompassed in energy, effort, and time spent on a brand, signifying consumers' active participation and interaction with the brand willing to take part in different brand-related initiatives, such as brand recommendations or social media interactions. Moreover, customer's actions and interactions with a brand's social media presence encompass various activities that indicate active participation and involvement with the brand's content and community among the key components of this dimension include likes and reactions, comments, shares, mentions, and tags, follow and subscriptions, clicks, user-generated content and participation in contests and promotion.

The findings conform with the studies based on the Social Exchange Theory by Thibaut and Kelley (1959, p. 196-205) this helps explain how customer engagement in social media influences firm performance. This theory suggests that SMEs engage with their audience on social media with the expectation of receiving benefits in return, such as increased customer loyalty and advocacy, and applied to elucidate how customer engagement in social media positively impacts firm performance by fostering reciprocal relationships with customers. SMEs aim to provide value to their audience through engaging content and, in return, expect improved growth and profitability.

Level of Firm Performance of selected SMEs in Tagum City

The overall mean score for the firm performance is 4.32 presented in Table 3 which can be described as very high with a 0.81 standard deviation. This indicates that the firm performance is very high in the items of growth and profitability performance.

Among the two indicators of growth and profitability, indicates that the profitability is very high with a mean of 4.36 and next followed by growth with a mean of 4.28. The result on the level of firm performance attests that SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte excellently handle and address issues that may affect the overall firm performance of their business.

Hence, profitability is a financial metric that reflects a company's capacity to generate profits and achieve its financial objectives. Moreover, it includes attaining profit goals, achieving a superior return on investment, and overall growth in total income, illustrating the financial health and success of the company over a specified period and a crucial aspect of firm performance of selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte aggressively pursuing to generate income relative to its expenses. Moreover, profitability is integral to an SME in Tagum City's overall performance, influencing its capacity to grow, compete, and sustain itself in the market.

Table 3. *Level of Firm Performance of selected Small-Medium Enterprises in the Tagum City, Davao del Norte*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Growth	4.28	0.82	High
Profitability	4.36	0.84	Very High
Overall	4.32	0.81	Very High

Finally, to support these findings, Harrigan et al. (2017, p.597-609) claimed that the possibility inherent in social media will positively affect sales growth. According to Seth (2012, p.1-20) reaching a great number of customers globally will contribute to internationalization and lead to high sales volume and consequently higher profitability.

Correlations between measures

Significance on the Relationship Between Content Marketing Strategy and Firm Performance

One of the objectives of this study is to determine the relationship between content marketing strategy, with a mean rating of 4.15, and firm performance, with a mean rating of 4.32 of selected SMEs in Tagum, City, Davao del Norte. Table 4 shows the significance of the relationship between the content marketing strategy and the firm performance of the selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. The relationship between the two variables was tested using the Pearson-r coefficient. Which shows a positive correlation with a computed r-value of the content marketing strategy, when correlated with firm performance, were 0.748 for content marketing strategizing context, 0.803 for content production context, 0.795 for content marketing performance measurement context and 0.823 for content marketing organization and probability level (p) is 0.001. With $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between content marketing strategy and firm performance was rejected.

Table 4. *Significant Relationship Between Content Marketing Strategy and Firm Performance of selected Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Tagum City, Davao del Norte*

Indicators	Dependent Variables	r-value	r ²	p-value	Decision
Content Marketing Strategizing Context	Firm Performance	0.748*	0.5595	0.001	Reject Ho
Content Production Context		0.803*	0.6448	0.001	Reject Ho
Content Marketing Performance Measurement Context		0.795*	0.6320	0.001	Reject Ho
Content Marketing Organization		0.823*	0.6773	0.001	Reject Ho

* $p < 0.05$

The results entail that a significant relationship exists between content marketing strategy and firm performance. This further means that the level of the content marketing strategy of the respondents has a relationship to their firm performance. This also signifies that there is a connection between the content marketing strategy of the respondents to their firm performance. This could probably mean that a high level of content marketing strategy corresponds to either a low or high level of firm performance of the respondents.

The findings conform with the theory of Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory by Barney, in the context of this study, content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media can be utilized to gain a competitive edge and encompass the creation of high-quality content, the enhancement of brand reputation, increased customer engagement, and the effective use of social media technologies. Moreover, the theory serves as the central foundation, emphasizing the importance of unique resources and capabilities, such as content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media, in shaping the competitive advantage and performance of SMEs.

Significance on the Relationship Between Customer Engagement in Social Media and Firm Performance

Another objective of this study is to determine the relationship between customer engagement in social media and the firm performance of selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. Table 5 determines the relationship of customer engagement in social media to the firm performance of the selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. As shown below, using statistical analysis and treatment, the relationship between the two variables was tested using the Pearson-r coefficient which shows a positive correlation with a computed r-value of customer engagement in social media when correlated with firm performance were 0.844 for cognitive dimension, 0.848 for emotional dimension, and 0.846 for behavioral dimension and probability level (p) is 0.001. With $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between customer engagement in social media and firm performance was therefore rejected.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship Between Customer Engagement in Social Media and Firm Performance of selected Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Tagum City, Davao del Norte*

Indicators	Dependent Variables	r-value	r ²	p-value	Decision
Cognitive Dimension	Firm Performance	0.844	0.7123	0.001	Reject Ho
Emotional Dimension		0.848	0.7191	0.001	Reject Ho
Behavioral Dimension		0.846	0.7157	0.001	Reject Ho

* $p < 0.05$

The results bring about the information that customer engagement in social media is highly related to firm performance. In the same manner, a connection between the level of customer engagement in social media and firm performance is established and observed. Moreover, the results further reveal that there is a reasonable relation between customer engagement in social media to firm performance, particularly for the respondents.

Lastly, the findings conform with the theory of The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), by Davis (1989, p. 319-340), which focuses on understanding the factors that influence users' acceptance and adoption of technology. In this study, TAM can be employed to investigate how the utilization of social media platforms, which are a form of technology, impacts the marketing strategies and ultimately the firm performance of SMEs and can explore how SMEs perceive the ease of using social media platforms for content marketing and the perceived usefulness of these platforms in achieving their marketing objectives. Additionally, TAM incorporates variables such as attitudes and behavioral intention, which can help elucidate the relationship between SMEs' adoption of social media

technologies and their overall firm performance.

Regression Analysis

Another objective of the study is to determine which domain of content marketing strategy on the firm performance in selected SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. This is with the aid of regression analysis. The test of significance was done further using the correlation approach with regression analysis, which clearly shows what domains of content marketing strategy significantly influence the firm performance.

Table 6.1. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of the Level of the Content Marketing Strategy on the Firm Performance of selected Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Tagum City, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE	Beta			
(Constant)	1.200	0.190		6.305	0.001	
Content Marketing Strategizing Context	0.074	0.094	0.065	0.783	0.435	Do not Reject Ho
Content Production Context	0.267	0.095	0.293*	2.812	0.005	Reject Ho
Content Marketing Performance Measurement Context	0.017	0.086	0.022	0.203	0.840	Do not Reject Ho
Content Marketing Organization	0.403	0.085	0.493*	4.761	0.001	Reject Ho

Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

*p<0.05 R-value = 0.841 R2 = 0.707 F-value = 135.151 p-value = 0.001

The results of the study, as shown in Table 6.1 above, indicated that the value is 0.707, as shown in the regression model. This explains that 70.7% of the total variability of firm performance is explained by four domains of content marketing strategy. The F-value is 135.151 with a p-value of <0.001, so there is a significant influence of content marketing strategy on firm performance. This further illustrates that the independent variable which is the content marketing strategy is a significant contributor to firm performance. The content production context and content marketing organization have p-values of 0.005 and 0.001 respectively (p<0.001). Based on these results per domain, then, the null hypothesis stating that no domain of content marketing strategy significantly influences firm performance was rejected. This shows that content production context and content marketing organization have a significant influence on firm performance. On the other hand, the content marketing strategizing context and content marketing performance measurement context had a p-value of 0.435 and 0.840, respectively (p>0.001), therefore, then the null hypothesis was accepted.

The results indicated that of the four domains of content marketing strategy, the content marketing organization had the greater influence on firm performance as it obtained a 0.493 beta coefficient, which is greater than the beta coefficient obtained by other domains such as content production context, content marketing strategizing context, and content marketing performance, which are 0.293, 0.065, and 0.022, respectively.

This denotes that content marketing organization indicates that organizational structures and processes are one of the major components contextualizing activities within an organization according to Porter and McLaughlin (2006, p.559-576). Moreover, according to the study of Lee J, et al. (2015, p.73-99), & Oslo EM et al. (2005 p.49-65) research on content marketing organization also highlights the importance of organizational structures and processes for marketing performance.

Table 6.2. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of the Level of the Customer Engagement in Social Media on the Firm Performance of selected Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Tagum City, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE	Beta			
(Constant)	1.843	0.104		17.783	0.001	
Cognitive Dimension	0.202	0.095	0.278*	2.131	0.034	Reject Ho
Emotional Dimension	0.253	0.090	0.363*	2.810	0.005	Reject Ho
Behavioral Dimension	0.163	0.103	0.230	1.591	0.113	Do not Reject Ho

Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

*p<0.05 R-value = 0.859 R2 = 0.738 F-value = 211.334 p-value = 0.001

The results of the study as shown in Table 6.2 indicated that the adjusted value is 0.738 as reflected in the regression model. This explains that 73.8% of the total variability of firm performance is explained by three domains of customer engagement in social media. The F-value is 211.334 with p<0.001, so, there is a significant influence on customer engagement in social media and firm performance. This further illustrates that the independent variable customer engagement in social media is a significant contributor to firm performance. The cognitive dimension and emotional dimension have p-values of 0.034 and 0.005, with p<0.05, then, the null hypothesis stating that no domain of customer engagement in social media significantly influences firm performance was rejected. This shows that the cognitive dimension and emotional dimension have a significant influence on firm performance. On the other hand, the behavioral dimension has a p-value of 0.113, with p>0.05, considered to be statistically significant, then the null hypothesis was not rejected.

The results indicated that of the three domains of customer engagement in social media, the third domain, namely emotional dimension,

has the greater influence on firm performance as it obtained a 0.363 beta coefficient, which is greater than the beta coefficient obtained by other domains such as cognitive dimension and behavioral, which are 0.278 and 0.230, respectively. Out of the three domains that explain the higher-order construct of customer engagement in social media, the emotional dimension was the strongest, affirming the emotional attachment, interest, pleasure, and fun that the customers are experiencing in their brand-related social media interactions. The second strongest domain was the cognitive dimension emerged as the strongest one, suggesting that customers are fully focused on their social media brand interactions and are stimulated to learn more about their favorite brand. The third is the behavioral dimension, indicating that customers are willing to take part in different brand-related initiatives.

Conclusions

The authors conclude based on the results that the level of content marketing strategy to firm performance of SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte has an overall rating of high when it comes to content marketing strategizing context, content production context, content marketing performance measurement context, and content marketing organization. Similarly, the level of customer engagement in social media to firm performance of SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte has a high level in terms of cognitive dimension, emotional dimension, and behavioral dimension. Finally, the level of firm performance of SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte has an overall rating of very high in the items of growth and profitability performance. In addition, the study found that there is a significant relationship between content marketing strategy and firm performance of SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. Moreover, it also makes clear which customer engagement in social media significant impact on the firm performance of SMEs in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. Based on the results per domain of content marketing strategy, it shows that content production context and content marketing organization have a significant influence on firm performance, effective content marketing can make the firm recognizable and provide a competitive edge in the field of business while cognitive dimension and emotional dimension domains of customer engagement in social media that showed significant influence on firm performance. Overall, both the content marketing strategy and customer engagement in social media have an important role in achieving firm performance.

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